

MAGISTRLAR CERTIFICATE

OF ACHIEVEMENT

... PROUDLY ...
PRESENTED TO

Hulkar Rajabova Farmonovna

TELEKANALLARNING KO'NGILOCHAR KORSATUVLARIDA(TOK-SHOU,REALITIV SHOU)

BOSHLOVCHINING NUTQIDAGI XATOLARNING NAZARIY TASNIFI

WEBSITE: WWW.REANDPUB.UZ

EMAIL: INFO@REANDPUB.UZ

2023/MAY

